

METHODS OF TEACHING LANGUAGE TO CHILDREN

Zubaydova Nilufar Negmatullayevna English teacher,
Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

Eshtemirova Gulsanam G'ulom qizi student, Samarkand state institute of foreign
languages

Abstract: This article discusses how to choose the right method for young learners, how to use methods. At the same time, it teaches how to use the appropriate method depending on the children's temperament.

Key words: Method, young learners, temperament, foreign languages, teaching style, method, nonlinguistic factors.

Nowadays, learning foreign languages has become an influential part of our life, however, it is affected by many nonlinguistic factors. Meanwhile teaching language to children is a multifaceted process that necessitates different methods and approaches tailored to their developmental stages and learning styles. Over the years, different science, theories and learning styles were developed in terms of teaching foreign languages. You will not find the best, the one and only method of teaching language to kids or adults. Choosing the correct teaching style depends on students' skills and abilities. So, in this article, I give some modern ideas on how to learn a new language and how to choose the proper method.

Here are some beneficial methods for teaching language to children:

1. Immersion Method
2. Interactive Play
3. Total Physical Response (TPR)
4. Story telling
5. Dialogue Journals
6. Scaffolding Techniques
7. Language Games
8. Visual aids
9. Songs and Rhymes
10. Cultural Contexts

1. Immersion Method

In the immersion approach, children are surrounded by the target language in a natural context. This method emphasizes listening and speaking from the very beginning, allowing children to pick up the language through exposure rather than direct instruction.

2. Interactive Play

Using games and fun activities in the lesson allows children to learn language faster and it increases their listening, comprehension, working with text and vocabulary.

3. Total Physical Response

This method is a combination of physical actions and language. Teachers give commands with new language and children respond with physical actions (ex: "clap", "jump"). This method helps strengthen understanding through kinesthetic learning.

4. Story Telling

Vocabulary is an important and necessary component of language acquisition. Vocabulary should be taught as one of the primary components from starting level (young learners) (Pinter,2006). Stories attract the attention of the child while creating text for new words. It can make it easier for children who is auditory learners by reading aloud.

5. Dialogue Journals

Dialogue writing method not only improves language skills, but also literacy skills in children.

6. Scaffolding Techniques

This method involves providing support that is gradually removed as children's skills improve. Teachers or caregivers might begin with more guidance before encouraging independent utilize of the language.

7. Language Games

Games such as bingo, matching pairs or word searches promote peer to peer communication and promote learning new language through playful games.

8. Visual aids

Utilizing pictures, flashcards, videos and other such visual aids help children to learn the connection between words and their meanings. This type of method is useful for children who is visual learners.

9. Songs and Rhymes

This type ensures faster memorization and correct pronunciation of words through music. Rhymes help you remember words longer.

10. Cultural contexts

By combining culture and language, you can learn about a new language and know about culture of that new language. For example, discussions about culture, traditional food or holidays increase vocabulary and broaden one's worldview.

Methodology is a science that acts as a bridge between the sum of knowledge given at the institute(university) and school experience (J.J.Jalolov.2012).

Conclusion. Each child is different therefore a combination of these methods is often most effectual in teaching languages to young learners. If the teacher knows how to work with pupils, the lesson will be full of fun. This article can help how to make entertaining atmosphere in the classroom. All the teacher can utilize these methods in order to achieve their teaching aims.

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